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Effectiveness of methods for controlling wild boar movement (wild boar separation): protocol for literature review and scenarios definition

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Abstract

The report proposes a working plan and a strategy to carry out an updated systematic review to assess the effectiveness of various methods for separation of wild boar population in different settings. Additionally, the approach to identify and define wild boar population separation scenarios is outlined. The effectiveness of these methods based on scientific literature and unpublished field experiences is assessed, taking into consideration types of fences, different spatial and temporal features, and eco-epidemiological scenarios with a focus on African Swine Fever (ASF) in the EU. Firstly, a semi-automated scientific literature review is conducted, involving creating search strings, defining inclusion and exclusion criteria, identifying relevant databases, and analysing results using specific software packages. To supplement findings from the literature review and collect unpublished field experiences, a questionnaire is distributed to wildlife professionals through the ENETWILD consortium. This will bring an insight into unpublished experiences and provide valuable case studies for scenarios identification, bolstering the assessment of the effectiveness of methods for controlling wild boar movement. In the context of ASF spread in Europe, our conclusions represent an additional tool to draw new and effective management strategies to control ASF spread and introduction.

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Key words: ASF management, wildlife management, wildlife epidemics management, fencing, wildlife population separation, landscape fragmentation

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Summary

In Europe, wild boar are the major African Swine Fever (ASF) reservoir. In an effort to control the spread of this disease, management strategies proposed include the separation of wild boar populations. In the context of the ENETWILD project, which specifically focuses on studying wildlife ecology and livestock-human-environment interactions to enhance disease surveillance, an update was requested to review the effectiveness of fencing methods or population separation methods for wild boar in different eco-epidemiological scenarios.

This report proposes a working plan and a strategy to carry out an updated systematic review on population separation methods for wild boar to assess the effectiveness of various methods in different settings. In addition, the approach to identify and define wild boar population separation scenarios is outlined.

The final report aims to assess the effectiveness evaluation of fences and other methods for controlling wild boar movement and consequently, the spread of ASF, in different scenarios through:

1. Collecting scientific evidence – gather evidence from peer-reviewed scientific literature and field experiences on the effectiveness of fences, natural barriers, and other methods (e.g. olfactory repellents) for controlling wild boar movement and ASF spread.
2. Identification and definition of scenarios – scenario identification for the use of fences to manage wild boar populations to define those applicable in Europe, considering factors such as fence types, ASF epidemiology, spatial and temporal variables of separation actions.

The effectiveness of these methods is evaluated based on the available scientific literature and unpublished field experiences, taking into consideration categories such as types of fences, different spatial and temporal features, and eco-epidemiological scenarios with a focus on ASF in the EU. Similarly, scenario identification and definition will be carried out using both published (from literature review) and unpublished data (from questionnaire).

Firstly, a semi-automated systematic scientific literature review is conducted. This will update and complement the information in EFSA AHAW Panel (2018). Hence, the consortium will optimise search strings, and perform searches in the same comprehensive set of databases from 2018 onwards. Once defined databases and inclusion and exclusion criteria the search results will be analysed with the aid of specific software packages. The Latent Dirichlet Allocation model, a machine learning technique, will be used for the first screening. The selected articles will undergo full-text screening by Consortium members for further refinement. The consortium will also perform snowballing, which involves following citations from included papers to find additional ones. The data from each selected paper will be extracted and stored in EFSA databases. This process will allow the integration of information provided in EFSA AHAW Panel (2018), which includes an extensive literature review on the same topic until that date, explicitly reporting effectiveness metrics. We will be able to discuss differences, and how the scenarios have evolved in light of the recent ASF outbreaks.

Secondly, a questionnaire will be submitted to relevant professional profiles (wildlife/hunting/agricultural agencies, wildlife managers, EUROBOAR members) to obtain information on unpublished data and field experiences, enriching the identification of different existing scenarios characterised by orography, land use, kind of fence high, mesh size, poles distances, etc.). The questionnaire is developed by the authors considering previous relevant work from EFSA and distributed through the ENETWILD consortium. Obtained results will be analysed and then presented in an online workshop where they will be discussed among selected participants to produce a final Delphi consensus. This will allow the integration of valuable additional data in the review, avoiding bias (positive) expected from the analysis of official publications.

The final steps will include a critical appraisal of the final bibliography, questionnaire results by Delphi consensus, and final data synthesis. We report all the different scenarios identified for the use of fences to manage wild boar populations, the relevant metrics to assess the effectiveness of different approach/methods and discuss potential future applications. The focus of the final discussion will be on: i) the effectiveness of fences and deterrents on the spatial behaviour of wild boar, including their effectiveness over time; ii) their impact on wild boar populations; iii) drawbacks and side effects of separation methods; iv) habituation phenomenon; v) and the socioeconomic and geopolitical implications of fencing.

In the context of ASF spread in Europe, our findings will serve as a basis for further investigations on separation methods and comparisons with other methods of ASF management, representing an additional tool to draw new and effective management strategies to control ASF spread and introduction.

1. Introduction

African Swine Fever (ASF) is a viral highly lethal infectious disease that affects pigs and wild boar, with no existing vaccine to combat the virus (Sauter-Louis et al., 2021). Wild boar populations have been identified as playing an important role in initiating outbreaks and as major reservoir of the disease (Tarasiuk & Giżejowski, 2021; Cadenas-Fernández et al., 2022); whilst human-related activities are mainly favouring the long distant spread (Guberti et al., 2022). Although the significance of various transmission modes in epidemiology remains unclear, several management strategies have been proposed, including those related to the reduction and separation of wild boar populations (EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018).

In wildlife epidemic management, an important intervention is the separation of target subpopulations from protected goods and other animal populations (Lee, 2023). Some examples are the veterinary cordon fence for mitigating foot-and-mouth disease in Namibia (Schneider, 2012), or specific natural barriers and fences in ASF-management in Europe (Pejsak et al., 2018; Licoppe et al., 2023). In the last case, other strategies have been employed as alternatives, such as the use of olfactory and gustatory repellents, or light and sound deterrents (EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018). However, their effectiveness varies depending on numerous factors such as fence characteristics (high, robustness, electrified or not), the timing of fence implementation, the extent, the context, and the landscape scale. The proliferation of ASF across various regions around the globe, accompanied by the significant increase in wild boar populations (native and introduced range), has incentivised the development of management plans and research projects to control its spread.

Systematic reviews provide thorough compilations of existing evidence pertinent to specific, well-defined questions, utilising standardised and predetermined methods to identify, critically appraise, and collate data from relevant studies (EFSA, 2010). This methodology presents an opportunity to ensure that the collection, documentation, and analysis of data from the incorporated studies are conducted rigorously and systematically. Thus, in this specific context, it allows for the evaluation of the effectiveness of various management strategies that have been implemented in recent years, specifically those related to controlling wild boar movement through separation methods and deterrents.

EFSA has reviewed the existing scientific evidence on the topic with the main conclusions that no large fences have been effective for the containment of wild suids (EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018). At the time of that report, some new large-scale fences were under construction, so an updated review of the available literature is an opportunity to evaluate their effectiveness in separating wild boar populations. Observations were provided on natural barriers, such as large rivers, as they have shown to reduce, but not completely impede, the movements of wild boar (EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018) Due to the spread of the ASF Virus (ASFV), and the high interest of the international community, new evidence has been made available. Therefore, the objective of the present work is to update the knowledge available until 2018, and to identify the different scenarios where those barriers have been applied and evaluate their effectiveness. The scenarios will be identified according to type of separation method, extent, landscape, timeline of implementation, aim of separation, epidemiological situation, outcome, and human-related

factors (of which definition for each will be provided), to be consistent with EFSA AHAW Panel (2018) and retrieve additional knowledge on the subject.

1.1 Background and Terms of Reference

The contract entitled "Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population, and environment (framework contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01) was awarded to the Universidad of Torino by EFSA. From here, we refer to this framework contract as to ENETWILD project. The specific objective 1 (SO1) of the framework contract refers "Wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment".

Due to the Art. 31 mandate from the European Commission about ASF risk factor analysis, EFSA requested ENETWILD consortium an update (to integrate the Scientific Opinion reported in EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018) regarding fencing methods, or population separation methods, available for wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) in different scenarios (e.g. type of separation method, extent, landscape, timeline of implementation, etc.) and implemented for different objectives (e.g. ASF control, crop protection, etc.). Therefore, the effectiveness of the different methods used for separating wild boar is evaluated based on information found in scientific literature, through a systematic review, and an *ad hoc* questionnaire distributed to relevant professional profiles (e.g. wildlife managers) across Europe. Specifically, deliverable 6.1b aims at collecting scientific evidence (literature review) for the effectiveness of fences and other methods (e.g. olfactory repellents) for controlling wild boar movement and consequently, the spread of ASF, considering the previous work from EFSA AHAW Panel (2018); deliverable 6.1 C aims at identifying and defining the different scenarios existing for the use of fences to manage wild boar populations, considering types of fences, epidemiological situations of ASF in the EU, location characteristics in the EU (orography, land use, etc).

This report will provide a working plan for the systematic literature review, including the protocol, and a proposed strategy for identifying scenarios from field experiences.

1.2 Scope of the report

The scope of the report is to illustrate:

- general working plan defining the questions, population, methodology, data needed, data analysis, and synthesis approach;
- step-by-step semi-automated scientific literature and literature review protocol;
- strategy for the *ad hoc* questionnaire and workshop for Delphi consensus to integrate unpublished field experiences;
- final report structure;
- timeline of the proposed work.

The scope of a second and final report will be to present the results gathered from literature and questionnaire in relation to the effectiveness of fences – and related deterrents – to affect the spatial behaviour of wild boar. In particular, these will include: (1) their effectiveness over time, (2) the clarity of the message of the barrier or deterrent as calibrated to wild boar sensory capacities, (3) across habituation and/or overexposure, and (4) side effects on other species as well as socioeconomic and geopolitical implications of fencing. Additionally, we will outline the

auxiliary, but crucial activities around fencing (e.g. ASF: including surveillance, active repelling and maintenance).

2. Methods

The ENETWILD consortium collects the scientific evidence from published literature with a semi-automated systematic literature review that will assess and synthesise research on the effectiveness of fences, deterrents and functional, symbolic, as well as natural barriers for controlling wild boar movements.

The identification of scenarios will be carried out primarily extracting relevant data from the identified publications, expanding the methodology used in EFSA AHAW Panel (2018). The parameters used to identify and define the scenarios will be collected in these macro categories:

- types of fences (physical, repellents, etc.);
- spatial features, including extent, permeability, and surrounding landscape characteristics (e.g. orography, land cover, land use, etc.);
- temporal features such as timeline of implementation, delays, etc.;
- aim of separation (e.g. ASF control, crop protection, etc.);
- eco-epidemiological context with a focus on ASF in the EU (e.g. other wildlife populations, information on pig/wild boar interface, etc.);
- human-related factors, including social and economic implications;
- outcome, including metric used to measure it.

The number of relevant publications is expected to be low, and literature review alone is not expected to bring significant new insight compared to the previously available data (in EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018). So, to better identify and define existing scenarios for the use of fences to manage wild boar populations, we will complete this analysis collecting data from professionals that have first-hand experiences on wild boar movement control through fencing or other natural or artificial barriers. To collect data on the macro categories listed before, ENETWILD consortium social scientists will elaborate an specific questionnaire to identify and collect unpublished field experiences and real-world application of wild boar separation methods. This questionnaire will be able to reveal aspects that in many cases are not fully reported in official documents, but are relevant to evaluate effectiveness, also in terms of costs-effectiveness, of wild boar separation methods (i.e. fix, temporary fence, electrified or not, time of fence realisation, time of fence durability, cost of realisation, cost of removal, cost of maintenance, effects on other species, environment -plains, hills, mountains- type of land use, habitat, ease of access of the fenced area). The questionnaire will be distributed to wildlife professionals and other relevant professionals by the ENETWILD consortium not only in countries affected by ASF, but in all the countries included in the Consortium. Respondents (i.e. wildlife/hunting/agricultural agencies, wildlife managers, EUROBOAR members) will be contacted directly, individually, through the ENETWILD partners network (mailing list, shared online folders, and, if required, guided interview will be conducted) to maximise data collection. The results obtained will be analysed and then presented in a workshop where they will be discussed among participants (selected from stakeholder that have participated in this task and suggested, if needed, by EFSA) to produce a final Delphi consensus. This will allow the integration of valuable additional data on

real-world scenarios in the review, avoiding bias (positive) expected from the analysis of official publications.

The effectiveness will be evaluated using the metrics provided in literature for the published data, and, for scenarios identified through questionnaires, effectiveness will be finally evaluated through expert opinion (Delphi consensus). A final re-evaluation with the critical appraisal of the final, integrated (literature and questionnaire/workshop), results will be provided.

2.1 General Working Plan

To comply to the ToR, we elaborated a general working plan which is reported hereafter:

Problem identification: wild boar numerical increase together with its biogeographical expansion and overlapping with human-driven ecological systems represent an important health and socio-economic issue. An example of health consequences is the current ASF epidemic while examples of the latter aspect are the damages caused by wild boar to agricultural production or road accidents. . The identified problem focuses on effectiveness of methods to segregate wild boar populations and to separate those from domestic animals (e.g. pig farms) to limit socio-economic damages and losses and the spread of ASFV.

Population: Wild boar *Sus scrofa* populations worldwide range, including introduced areas.

Data needed: Data to be extracted from literature and from questionnaire are the following: 1) reference, 2) study description (type, date, duration), 3) data describing separation methods, 4) location description: location (e.g. coordinates, area), scenario, density, behaviour of animals, 5) methods description quantifying effectiveness and separation 6) data describing other effects, 7) economic information 8) subjective findings (e.g. results, conclusion), 9) additional comments (Table 3). These data will be necessary to the are used to classify the scenarios in the macro categories.

Methodology: Systematic literature review based on specific and flexible search strategy (Table 1) and pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria to screen the search results and select the most relevant studies (Table 2) to update EFSA on pre-existing knowledge on the subject (EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018). Databases selected are Web of Science and Scopus (in agreement with EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018), with the addition of Scholar, Embase, and PubMed. In addition to the systematic literature review, relevant data will be retrieved by distributing an aimed questionnaire to professionals in the field of wildlife management/health to gather additional information on existing scenarios. Data collected will be presented in a workshop with selected respondents to produce a Delphi consensus. Scenarios will be identified and defined from those two sources according to the abovementioned macro categories.

Analysis: data extraction, critical appraisal to evaluate the quality and reliability of the selected studies, synthesis of the findings from the selected studies. Data extraction from questionnaire results, presentation in a readable format to a workshop, final Delphi consensus. Integration of the final synthesis from literature and Delphi consensus. These will involve a narrative summary,

thematic analysis, qualitative and quantitative analyses (these to be chosen according to the final data structure and availability).

2.2 Step-by-step semi-automated scientific literature review

For the semi-automated review of the scientific literature, we have:

- Created naïve search strings based on a priori knowledge of the topic and review question (Table 1), based on keywords and strings from EFSA AHAW Panel (2018), who have already reviewed and evaluated the existing scientific literature on wild boar population reduction measures, wild boar movement restriction, and wild boar population separation methods in different scenarios until 2018.
- Defined inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 2).
- Extended the search by new keywords according to recent experiences.
- Identified relevant databases like PubMed, Web of Science, Embase, Scopus, and Scholar based on the formerly used databases (EFSA AHAW Panel 2018).
- Performed search in a subset of databases with naïve strings and exported results.
- Analysed results by using the *litsearchr* package (Grames et al. 2019) in R (R Core Team, 2023), and, after eliminating duplicates, extracted real keywords and keywords detected through a function using the Rapid Automatic Keyword Extraction (RAKE) algorithm (a domain independent keyword extraction algorithm which tries to determine key phrases in a body of text by analysing the frequency of word appearance and its co-occurrence with other words in the text). Plotted document feature matrix and chosen cut-off to analyse the resulting list of keywords.
- Optimised definitive string search based on cut-off optimisation (long composite strings elimination and manual analysis by terms group, Jaspers et al. 2018), in addition comparison with the string used in EFSA AHAW Panel (2018) to create more complex and direct strings (see overview in Table 1).
- Identified partners willing to participate and review adequate numbers of papers to be screened in full text.

The future steps will include:

- Performing search in all databases from 2018 (included) and analysing results with the *revtools* R package (Westgate 2019): eliminate duplicates by title and DOI, eliminate citations, reviews, and conference papers to retain only original work in articles, theses, and book chapters, keeping only relevant languages.
- Screening remaining articles by topic (using Latent Dirichlet Allocation model), title and abstract (reiteratively if necessary), according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 2). We use this approach for a first screening to avoid the risk of eliminating relevant articles. Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is a Bayesian algorithm used in Natural Language Processing (NLP), which is a machine learning technique to analyse human language. NLP is a specific component of Text Mining (TM), which performs a special kind of linguistic analysis that comes down to helping a machine read text. Once the articles are transformed into a suitable input format the machine-learning algorithm, in this case,

LDA, can be employed to determine which of the retrieved articles are relevant for the study and which articles can be omitted in any further analysis (sensu Jaspers et al. 2018).

- Manual full-text screening to refine the selection according to inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 2) and allowing data collection to synthesise relevant information.
- Performing snowballing (follow citations from included papers to find additional ones) (Jaspers et al. 2018).
- Provide each partner with a data model (Table 3) to be filled in with data from each selected paper, and a guideline. Data extracted this way will provide the basis for the systematic literature review, and will constitute a database compatible and comparable with EFSA AHAW Panel (2018), which will be transferred to EFSA storage systems.
- Finalise critical appraisal of the final bibliography, data synthesis designing a comparable table to Table A.5 in Appendix A.2 from EFSA AHAW Panel (2018), and listing of the different scenarios existing for the use of fences to manage wild boar populations.

2.3 Scenario identification: *ad hoc* questionnaire and workshop

- Create the aimed questionnaire with the aid of the ENETWILD consortium social scientists.
- Distribute questionnaire to wildlife professionals and other relevant professionals using the ENETWILD network, contacting people individually and conducting guided interview if necessary.
- Collect and analyse respondents answers.
- Organise a workshop with participants selected from stakeholder that have participated in this task and to discuss questionnaire outcome and produce a final Delphi consensus.

The final task is the finalisation of the report with the integration of the two sources of data.

Table 1: Summary table of the review questions, the naïve string searches, and the definitive strings.

Review question	Target	Terms group	Naïve string	Definitive string
Effectiveness (incl. practical applicability, cost-effectiveness and efficiency) of fencing methods, or other population separation methods (as well as natural barriers), available for wild boar in different scenarios (e.g. for protecting forest, farmland, pig holdings, urban areas, highways) in the context or prevention and control of ASF	topic title abstract keywords	population	"feral pig" OR "feral pigs" OR boar* OR swine OR hog OR hogs OR scrofa OR wildboar* OR "wild boar*" OR "wild pig"	"feral pig" OR "feral pigs" OR "wild pig" OR boar* OR swine OR hog OR hogs OR scrofa OR wildboar* OR "wild boar*" OR "wild pig" ^Δ
	topic title abstract keywords	method	fenc* OR barrier* OR repel* OR odor fence OR odour fence OR optical fence OR acoustic repel* OR restrain* OR trench* OR ditch* OR channel* OR river* OR "management strateg*" OR gunning OR shoot* OR trap* OR snar* OR hunt* OR track* OR harvest* OR poison* OR feed* OR bait* OR steriliz* OR sterilis* OR "fertility control*" OR permeability	fenc* OR barrier* OR repel* OR restrain* OR "natural barrier*" OR "management strateg*" OR shoot* OR trap* OR hunt* OR track* OR harvest* OR poison* OR feed* OR bait* OR steriliz* OR sterilis* OR "fertility control*" OR "separation method*" OR permeability
	topic title abstract keywords	process	separat* OR move* OR moving OR dispers* OR "population structur*" OR control OR "population management" OR "population density" OR "population reduction" OR "population separation" OR decreas* OR lower* OR limit* OR depopulat* OR cull* OR eliminat* OR extermin*	separat* OR dispers* OR "population structur*" OR "population control" OR "population management" OR "population density" OR "population reduction" OR "population separation" OR decreas* OR lower* OR limit* OR depopulat* OR cull* OR eliminat* OR extermin*

(Δ) An additional search for the term "warthog" will be included for the discussion in comparison to feral *Sus scrofa*.

Table 2: List of inclusion and exclusion criteria for the worldwide literature review to gather comparable results to EFSA AHAW Panel (2018), so that results can integrate existing knowledge and can be compared to identify differences across time.

Inclusion criteria (aimed review)	Exclusion criteria (aimed review)
Separation methods for wild boar or feral pig populations	Separation methods for other wildlife populations
Quantitative or qualitative evaluation of a natural or artificial barrier, reviews excluded	Discussion of a natural or artificial barrier without clear evaluation of barrier effectiveness and review articles
Publication dated 2018 (incl.) onwards (as to compare to results of EFSA AHAW Panel 2018)	Publication older than 2017 (included)
Inclusion criteria (additional discussion)	
Separation methods for other ungulate populations (incl. deer and warthog)	
Also use publication older than 2018	

Table 3: Example of spread sheet to be provided to partners for data extraction (modified from Table A5 in Appendix A.2 in EFSA AHAW Panel, 2018) and for designing the summary table of literature review (#).

Reference	Type of study	Method								Method description	Location*		Area size
		Electric fence	Solid fence	Odour	sound	light	gustatory	Natural barrier (specify)	Other (specify)		Country	Locality (coordinate)	
										Describe all methods included in the study			km ²

Table 3: (continued I)

Species		Type of response: population (specify density, abundance etc.)	Type of response: Behaviour of animals	other effects (target and other species, please specify)				landscape	Scenarios identification as reported in EFSA AHAW Panel (2018)
target species	secondary species (specify)	specify density, abundance etc., name numbers if applicable	describe methods how behaviour of animals was measured	describe how animals reacted	population separation (ecological aspects)	genetic inference	hindered migration	other (specify)	Summary of the scenario evaluation as reported in the above reference

Table 3: (continued II)

Period		Method estimation effectiveness	Separation measures	Results	ASF-infected area	economic information	short comment
Start (MMYYYY)	Stop (MMYYYY)	Describe parameter(s)	Parameter(s) quantified to estimate results	Quantitative data or qualitative remarks	Y/N (if yes, zone type)	costs in €, \$ etc.	additional notes

#different scenarios for type of study, country, landscape, specification, etc. will be included in drop down menus. Vocabulary and definitions will be included. For ENETWILD partners filling the table: *If multiple/paired study sites (e.g. with different scenarios, control, before-after) within one reference please fill one row per study site/situation if applicable.

2.4 Final report structure

A report discussing the findings will be submitted to EFSA supporting publications, structured as follows:

- Abstract
- Summary
- Introduction
- Background and Terms of Reference
- Methodology for the semi-automated literature review
- Analysis of the results from the semi-automated literature review
- Discussion of effectiveness of methodologies and different applications in infected and non-infected areas, as well as remarks on artificial versus natural barriers and different scenarios that emerge from the semi-automated literature review
- Methodology for the questionnaire on the available field experiences with relevant stakeholder, workshop, and Delphi consensus
- Analysis of the results from the stakeholder responses
- Report of the workshop including results of the discussion and Delphi consensus outcome (effectiveness evaluated from Delphi consensus)
- Final discussion of effectiveness of methodologies and different applications in infected and non-infected areas with re-evaluation and critical appraisal of the integrated (literature and questionnaire/workshop) information gathered
- Conclusions

2.5 Timeline

3. Conclusion

Due to the experiences with fencing during ASF outbreaks in the EU we assume that new insights in the effectiveness as well as on the side effects of fencing will be presented. Thanks to the expertise and the wide and established network of the ENETWILD consortium, the work will be conducted according to the timeline provided to meet the required deadline. The questionnaire design will be starting immediately. The results obtained from both, literature review and questionnaire, will be available by the end of February 2024, and will be discussed during the workshop. In this way, we will be able to include final suggestions on the effectiveness and

feasibility of wild boar separation methods in different scenarios, their costs, side effects on other species before the submission of the report. The outcome, integrating published and unpublished scenarios, will draw the state of the art of available experiences, allowing to reflect on the best scenarios to be applied in the different circumstances to control wild boar movement and, consequently, ASF spread.

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